

Disease severity, clinical characteristics, and disease control in patients with chronic spontaneous urticaria across different therapeutic modalities: A cross-sectional study in Iraqi patients

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Abstract

Chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU) is a dermatological condition associated with substantial burden and impaired quality of life. This cross-sectional observational study evaluated disease severity and control among patients with CSU receiving different therapeutic regimens. A total of 101 patients were included, with a mean age of 31.9 years. Patients were allocated to monotherapy (n = 51) or combination therapy (n = 50). Angioedema was present in 58.4% of participants. Disease severity was comparable between groups, with median Urticaria Severity Scores of 43 and 46, respectively (p = 0.596). Disease control was generally poor, with median Urticaria Control Test scores of 5 and 6 (p = 0.447), and uncontrolled disease observed in approximately 84% of patients. A significant inverse correlation was observed between severity and disease control, indicating that higher symptom severity was associated with poorer control.

Keywords

Chronic spontaneous urticaria, Disease Control, Disease Severity, Quality of Life, Exacerbating Factors

Introduction

Chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU) impacts 1% of the global population (Kolkhir et al. 2018; Fok et al. 2021), and significantly diminishes patients' quality of life (Xiang et al. 2023). The sudden and unpredictable appearance of wheals and angioedema, as well as pruritus, are the primary factors responsible for the physical, social, and emotional impact of CSU (Gonçalo et al. 2021). These symptoms markedly affect various dimensions of patients' health-related quality

of life, with health status scores of CSU patients reported to be analogous to those of individuals with coronary artery disease concerning work performance, sleep disturbances, emotional responses, and social interactions (Asero et al. 2024). Research in several regions globally indicates a prevalent deficiency in health-seeking behavior among patients afflicted with skin diseases (Al-Battat and Taie 2016). While urticaria is currently a public health concern in the Middle East, it remains underrepresented in the region (Tawil et al. 2023). A comprehensive examination of the rising

burden of CSU may assist in addressing medical care challenges in this region (Balp et al. 2025). Consequently, population-based studies delineating the clinical characteristics and impact of CSU, together with real-world patient experiences, are essential (Kolkhir et al. 2023).

The international urticaria guideline outlines a systematic approach to systemic therapy for CSU, incorporating second-generation H1 antihistamines, omalizumab (an anti-IgE monoclonal antibody), and cyclosporine (Bernstein et al. 2014). In the Joint Task Force (JTF) guidelines, additional considerations in step 2 include the addition of a second-generation antihistamine, an H2 antagonist, a leukotriene receptor antagonist, or a first-generation antihistamine for nighttime use (Shahzad Mustafa and Sánchez-Borges 2018). The World Allergy Organization (WAO) and European Academy of Allergy and Clinical Immunology (EAACI) guidelines do not support these additions due to insufficient evidence (Shahzad Mustafa and Sánchez-Borges 2018). Nevertheless, over 50% of patients fail to attain illness control with H1-antihistamines, and as many as 34% do not react to omalizumab therapy (Riedl et al. 2025). A global real-world study reported that 84% had inadequate disease control even after dose adjustment or antihistamine (Bernstein et al. 2025). Clinical evidence indicates that omalizumab significantly improves disease activity and control scores compared to baseline, achieving better control in many CSU patients (Chen et al. 2021). These findings demonstrate the importance of assessing disease severity and control across different treatment regimens. Assessment instruments can enhance communication between patients and providers regarding the existence and intensity of symptoms (Ahmed et al. 2024). Epidemiological studies on CSU patients' clinical, and psychological features are limited in Iraq. Lack of standardized illness severity and control assessments limits individualized treatment regimens. Due to budget constraints and restricted availability to sophisticated biologics, this gap demands optimal therapy use and patient outcomes monitoring. Evaluating patients' CSU management efficacy with different therapy modalities will fill considerable gaps. This study was designed to evaluate; the effectiveness of two major therapeutic regimens used for treatment of CSU as a general practice. The aim of the study is to subjectively assess the patients' symptoms severity and disease control among a sample of Iraqi patients presenting with CSU.

Method

Study design and participants

The current study was a cross-sectional observational study conducted from September 2024 to April 2025. It included a sample of 101 patients diagnosed previously with chronic spontaneous urticaria at the Specialized Al-

ergy Center and Al-Shaheed Al-Sadr General Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq.

Inclusion Criteria were: Patients (aged ≥ 15) diagnosed with CSU according to the European (EAACI/GA²LEN/EuroGuiDerm/APAAACI) guideline for urticaria (Zuberbier et al. 2022), and receiving treatment strategies of treatment according to the U.S. urticaria guideline (JTF urticaria practice parameter) (Jugessur 2022), for at least 4 weeks. Patients with the following criteria: Patients had other dermatological conditions, isolated chronic inducible urticaria or receiving other medication that may cause skin adverse effects, using additional herbal or complementary treatments for urticarial were excluded.

Study groups and data collection

The study enrolled a convenient sample size comprising a total of 121 patients, 20 individuals excluded because of poor compliance with any medication or study protocol, 101 patients fulfil the inclusion criteria and were included. Patients were randomly allocated to two groups according to their treatment.

Group A: Patients received first-generation or second-generation antihistamines (monotherapy).

Group B: Patients received combination therapy.

The researcher collected data using a validated Arabic version or an Arabic-translated questionnaire, and the validity was tested in a pilot study. Data were obtained via in-person interviews with individuals after securing their consent. A data collection sheet was utilized to gather the necessary information for the investigation.

A pilot trial, conducted over three weeks at the Allergy Center and Al-Shaheed Al-Sadr General Hospital, randomly chosen fifteen patients who were not included in the study. The face validation conducted was to meet the criteria for study enrolment, ascertain the clarity of the translated questionnaire, and evaluate the necessity for modifications to the subjective instruments of the study.

The reliability assessment using Cronbach's alpha revealed that the translated questionnaire on patients urticaria severity score (USS) scored 0.701 indicating good internal consistency for the study instrument (Jugessur 2022).

Assessment of urticaria severity

Patients' disease severity was assessed by using Urticaria Severity Score questionnaire (USS) translated into Arabic. USS was designed as 9 major items questionnaire according to how skin affected patient life over past week. Higher scores indicated increased symptom severity and related lifestyle impairment (Jariwala et al. 2009).

Assessment of urticaria control test

The evaluation of disease control was conducted using the Urticaria Control Test (UCT) Arabic version. The overall score varies from 0 (indicating no illness control) up to 16

Table 1. Demographics and clinical characteristics stratified by study groups.

Variable	Total		Group A N = 51		Group B N = 50		p- value	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
Age	Median (IQR)	29	(15–79)	30	(15–79)	26	(15–56)	0.016*
Age groups	≤17	15	14.9%	4	7.8%	11	22.0%	0.075
	18–39	57	56.4%	29	56.9%	28	56.0%	
	40–64	26	25.7%	15	29.4%	11	22.0%	
	≥65	3	3.0%	3	5.9%	0	0.0%	
Sex	Female	68	67.3%	29	56.9%	39	78.0%	0.024
	Male	33	32.7%	22	43.1%	11	22.0%	
BMI	Mean ± SD	27.19	± 5.41	27.3	± 5.8	27.1	± 5.0	0.446*
	Illiterate	4	4.0%	3	5.9%	1	2.0%	
Education status	Primary	32	31.7%	23a	45.1%	9a, b	18.0%	0.002
	High school	51	50.5%	19 a	37.3%	32 a, b	64.0%	
	College	9	8.9%	6	11.8%	3	6.0%	
	High education	5	5.0%	0 a	0.0%	5 a, b	10.0%	
Smoking	No	82	81.2%	38	74.5%	44	88.0%	0.083
	Yes	19	18.8%	13	25.5%	6	12.0%	
Residence	Urban	86	85.1%	41	80.4%	45	90.0%	0.175
	Rural	15	14.9%	10	19.6%	5	10.0%	
Family history	No	74	73.30%	33	64.70%	41	82.00%	0.050
	Yes	27	26.70%	18	35.30%	9	18.00%	
Comorbid	Absent	51	50.50%	23	45.10%	28	56.00%	0.273
	Present	50	49.50%	28	54.90%	22	44.00%	

Data presented as Number (N) and percentage (%). P-value by Chi square test or Fisher's Exact Test as appropriate, * P-value by Mann Whitney test. Superscript letter denotes a subset of groups categories whose column proportions differ significantly from each other at the 0.05 level by Bonferroni post hoc test. BMI: Body mass index. SD: Standard Deviation.

(indicating complete disease control) (Weller et al. 2014). Urticaria that is inadequately controlled is classified as < 12 as a cutoff value, while urticaria that is well controlled is classified as ≥ 12.

Ethical consideration

The study protocol was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee of Mustansiriyah University's College of Pharmacy (Research No. 94, Approval No. 81), and agreement of the Specialized Allergy Center and Al-Shaheed Al-Sadr General Hospital in Baghdad were achieved. Informed written consent was acquired from all participants.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted utilizing SPSS version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, N.Y., USA). Continuous variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). The normality of the sample was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test ($P < 0.05$), indicated non-normal distribution. Comparative analyses among groups were conducted utilizing the Mann-Whitney U test and the Kruskal-Wallis test for continuous variables, if warranted. Categorical variables were evaluated using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. Bivariate relationships between clinical scores and other variables were assessed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

Results

Demographics and clinical characteristics

A total of 101 patients with chronic urticaria were enrolled in the study, with a mean age of 31.9 ± 13.8 years Interquartile Range (IQR: 15–79). Overall, there was a female predominance, with a male-to-female ratio of 1:2.6. All participants demographic parameters are presented in Table 1.

Features of chronic spontaneous urticaria

The clinical features of chronic urticaria were not significantly associated with the treatment pattern, whether monotherapy or combination therapy. Although the disease duration appeared longer in Group B (8.5 months) compared to Group A (5 months), this difference did not reach statistical significance, Table 2.

Treatment protocol and anticipated side effect

Antihistamines were commonly used in both groups; however, second-generation antihistamines were significantly more preferred in Group B, with 43 patients (87%) receiving them compared to 29 patients (56.9%) in Group A ($p = 0.002$). The number of drug combinations prescribed ranged from two to five. Most patients (36, 72%) received two drugs. Side effects were more frequently

Table 2. Chronic Spontaneous urticaria features stratified by study groups.

Variable	Total		Group A N = 51		Group B N = 50		P value	
	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Duration of disease (month)	Median (IQR)	6	(3–12)	5	(3–12)	8.5	(3–12)	0.336*
Angioedema presence	No	42	41.60%	20	39.20%	22	44.00%	0.626
	Yes	59	58.40%	31	60.80%	28	56.00%	
Angioedema sites	Eye	46	78.00%	23	74.20%	23	82.10%	0.172
	Lips	44	74.60%	20	64.50%	24	85.70%	
	Throat	7	11.90%	4	12.90%	3	10.70%	
	Hand	2	3.40%	0	0.00%	2	7.10%	
	0	42	41.60%	20	39.20%	22	44.00%	
No. of Angioedema site	1	24	23.80%	17	33.30%	7	14.00%	0.130
	2	30	29.70%	12	23.50%	18	36.00%	
	3	5	5.00%	2	3.90%	3	6.00%	
	0	20	19.80%	12	23.50%	8	16.00%	
Exacerbation factor No	1	27	26.70%	12	23.50%	15	30.00%	0.773
	2	30	29.70%	15	29.40%	15	30.00%	
	3	23	22.80%	12	23.50%	11	22.00%	
	4	1	1.00%	0	0.00%	1	2.00%	
Exacerbating Factors	Stress	53	65.40%	26	66.70%	27	64.30%	0.808
	Food	44	54.30%	23	59.00%	21	50.00%	
	Cold	15	18.50%	6	15.40%	9	21.40%	
	Heat	48	59.30%	23	59.00%	25	59.50%	
Time of symptoms appear	Exercise	1	1.20%	1	2.60%	0	0.00%	0.93
	Any time	53	52.50%	26	51.00%	27	54.00%	
	Morning	9	8.90%	5	9.80%	4	8.00%	
	Night	39	38.60%	20	39.20%	19	38.00%	

Data presented as Number (N) and percentage (%). P-value by Chi square test or Fisher's Exact Test as appropriate. * P-value by Mann Whitney test.

reported in Group B, with only 12 patients (24%) indicating no side effects, compared to 23 patients (45.1%) in Group A, as further detailed in Table 3.

Urticaria severity score and associated factors

Patients' responses to the USS questionnaires are summarized in Fig. 1. While the number of antihistamines and corticosteroids used, defining characteristics of Group B, distinguished the groups, sleep disturbances due to hives and itching were significantly more prevalent in Group A. The median total USS score for Group A was 43 (IQR: 31–54), which did not differ significantly from Group B's median score of 46 (IQR: 34–51), $p = 0.596$.

The body regions most commonly associated with itching or hives, whether on average or on the worst day, were the extremities, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Disease-related characteristics were significantly associated with USS severity. The presence of angioedema and the number of affected sites were both significantly associated with increased USS scores ($p < 0.001$). Patients with angioedema had a mean USS score of 49.1 ± 13 , significantly higher than those without angioedema (35.8 ± 11.3 ; $P < 0.001$). The number of exacerbating factors was significantly associated with USS scores ($p = 0.020$). Patients reporting one exacerbating factor

had lower USS scores (37.2 ± 12.37) than those with none (49.6 ± 16.68 ; adjusted post hoc $p < 0.02$). Further details are illustrated Table 4.

The urticaria control score and associated factors

The response of patients to UCT questionnaire are summarized in Fig. 3. Patients in group A experienced more severe disruptions to their quality of life due to urticaria, with a higher proportion reporting extreme impact. In contrast, Group B patients tended to report milder or moderate effects. The median UCT score of Group B was higher than that of A Group (6 vs 5) but statistically not significant. Overall, only 16 Patient exhibited good disease control while the rest 85 scored as uncontrolled, there was no difference in UCT scores between group A and B, $p = 0.966$.

Among patients with well-controlled disease, half belonged to Group A and the other half to Group B. The highest proportion of uncontrolled cases, 53 patients (62.4%), were young adults aged 18–39 years. In contrast, the majority of patients with well-controlled disease, 9 individuals (56.3%), were aged between 40 and 65 years. Other disease-related factors showed no statistically significant association with UCT classification groups, Table 5.

Figure 1. Urticaria severity score items stratified by study groups.

Figure 2. Parts of the body where the hives or itch, on average or the most stratified by the study groups.

Correlation of clinical and demographic factors and clinical scores

Within Group A, a moderate positive correlation was observed between total UCT score and disease duration ($r = 0.407, p = 0.003$), suggesting that longer disease duration was associated with higher UCT scores. In contrast, Group B demonstrated a weak inverse correlation between total UCT score and disease duration ($r = -0.283, p = 0.047$), indicating that longer disease duration was associated with

lower UCT scores. In Group A, a significant inverse correlation with UCT was evident for USS ($r = -0.474$), Table 6.

Discussion

In the present study, most of the CSU patients enrolled were female with prevalence of middle age, particularly peaking between 18–39 years of age, which aligns with previous findings (Maurer et al. 2016). The findings align

Figure 3. Urticaria control score items stratified by study groups.

Table 3. Treatment Protocol stratified by study groups.

Variable		Total		Group A N = 51		Group B N = 50		P-value
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
Duration of treatment (weeks)	Median (IQR)	4	(4-4)	4	(4-8)	4	(4-4)	0.251*
Antihistamine	1 st gen	46	46.00%	22	43.10%	24	49.00%	0.002
	2 nd gen	72	72.00%	29	56.90%	43	87.80%	
Drug combinations	Combination+ Two types of 2 nd gen	13	31.70%	0	0.00%	13	31.70%	-
	Combination+ leukotriene R. antagonist	14	34.10%	0	0.00%	14	34.10%	
	Combination+ H2 receptor antagonist	4	9.80%	0	0.00%	4	9.80%	
	Combination+ corticosteroid	22	53.70%	0	0.00%	22	53.70%	
Overall number of medications	1	51	50.50%	51	100.00%	0	0.00%	<0.001
	2	36	35.60%	0	0.00%	36	72.00%	
	3	12	11.90%	0	0.00%	12	24.00%	
	4	1	1.00%	0	0.00%	1	2.00%	
	5	1	1.00%	0	0.00%	1	2.00%	
Frequency of drug administration/day	Median (range)	1	(1-3)	1	(1-2)	1	(1-3)	<0.001*
Topical treatment use	None	86	85.10%	46	90.20%	40	80.00%	0.15
	Yes	15	14.90%	5	9.80%	10	20.00%	
	0	35	34.70%	23 ^a	45.10%	12 ^{a, b}	24.00%	
No. of side effects	1	23	22.80%	11	21.60%	12	24.00%	0.042
	2-3	16	15.80%	9	17.60%	7	14.00%	
	>3	27	26.70%	8 ^a	15.70%	19 ^{a, b}	38.00%	
side effects	Drowsiness			18	35%	15	30%	
	Fatigue			10	20%	22	44%	
	Dizziness			8	16%	20	40%	

Data presented as Number (N) and percentage (%). P-value by Chi square test or Fisher's Exact Test as appropriate. * P-value by Mann Whitney test. Superscript letter denotes a subset of groups categories whose column proportions differ significantly from each other at the .05 level by Bonferroni post hoc test.

Table 4. Association of clinical and demographic factors association with total USS.

Variable	Total USS score		P value	
	Mean	±SD		
Groups	Group A	42.6	13.5	0.596*
	Group B	44.5	14.4	
Age groups	≤17	39.5	16.7	0.12†
	18–39	44.9	12.8	
	40–64	41.6	14.2	
	≥65	54.3	14.2	
Sex	Female	44.9	13.1	0.15*
	Male	40.8	15.3	
Angioedema presence	No	35.8	11.3	<0.001*
	Yes	49.1	13.0	
No. of Angioedema site	0	35.8 a	11.3	<0.001†
	1	47.6 a, b	13.3	
	2	48.5 a, c	13.1	
	3	59.4 a, d	5.9	
No. of Exacerbation factor	0	49.6 a	16.68	0.020†
	1	37.2 a, b	12.37	
	2	42.7	12.38	
	3	46.5	12.65	
	4	52	.	

Data presented as Mean ± SD. P-value by *Mann Whitney test, †Kruskal Wallis test. Superscript letters denote a subset of groups which differ significantly from each other at the 0.05 level by Bonferroni post hoc test. SD: Standard Deviation.

with previous studies that indicates a prevalence of CSU that is twice as high in females (Barzilai et al. 2023), consistent with the current study. The observed gender difference is attributed to the influences of sex hormones and autoimmunity (Jo et al. 2022). Regarding the disease features the CSU duration of six months was shorter than reported in other studies. This difference might be due to the specific characteristics of the study group or variation in study design. A recent study in Turkey stated a median disease duration of twelve months in a group of 589 adults with CSU (Özçeker et al. 2023). The prevalence of angioedema ranges from approximately 33% to 67% among adults with CSU (Stepaniuk et al. 2020). In the current study observation rate was 58.4%, consistent with a study conducted in Israel found that the prevalence of angioedema was 54.7% in CSU-associated angioedema, based on a sample of 170 adult patients (Sokolovskis et al. 2024), And 59.8% in another study (Zuberbier et al. 2018). Most patients in the present study reported stress as an exacerbation factor followed by heat and food. This aligns with study conducted in Canada involved 72 patients which revealed persistent patterns in urticaria triggers with Stress reported as substantial trigger (Stepaniuk et al. 2020). Despite possible regional or cultural variations, specific urticaria triggers such as tension, heat, and food additives are consistently identified across various studies, owing to several fundamental factors (Shah et al. 2022). Likewise,

Table 5. Association of clinical and demographic factors association with UCT groups.

Variable	Total	Uncontrolled		well controlled		p-value	
		n = 85		n = 16			
		No.	%	No.	%		
Groups	Group A	51	43	50.6%	8	50.0%	0.966
	Group B	50	42	49.4%	8	50.0%	
Age groups	≤17	15	12	14.1%	3	18.8%	0.012
	18–39	57	53 a	62.4%	4 a, b	25.0%	
	40–64	26	17 a	20.0%	9 a, b	56.3%	
	≥65	3	3	3.5%	0	0.0%	
Sex	Female	68	57	67.1%	11	68.8%	0.895
	Male	33	28	32.9%	5	31.3%	
Comorbid	None	51	41	48.2%	10	62.5%	0.295
	Yes	50	44	51.8%	6	37.5%	
Angioedema presence	No	42	33	38.8%	9	56.3%	0.194
	Yes	59	52	61.2%	7	43.8%	
No. of Angioedema site	0	42	33	38.8%	9	56.3%	0.512
	1	24	22	25.9%	2	12.5%	
	2	30	25	29.4%	5	31.3%	
	3	5	5	5.9%	0	0.0%	
Exacerbation factor No	0	20	16	18.8%	4	25.0%	0.387
	1	27	20	23.5%	7	43.8%	
	2	30	27	31.8%	3	18.8%	
	3	23	21	24.7%	2	12.5%	
Time of symptoms appear	4	1	1	1.2%	0	0.0%	0.549
	Any time	53	44	51.8%	9	56.3%	
	Morning	9	9	10.6%	0	0.0%	
	Night	39	32	37.6%	7	43.8%	

Data presented as Number (N) and percentage (%). P-value by Chi square test or Fisher's Exact Test as appropriate. Superscript letters denote a subset of groups which differ significantly from each other at the 0.05 level by Bonferroni post hoc test.

Table 6. Correlation of clinical and demographic factors and clinical scores.

	USS Total	P-value	UCT Total	P-value
Group A n = 51				
Age	0.032	0.822	0.113	0.429
BMI	0.082	0.567	0.123	0.39
No. of SE	0.113	0.43	0.055	0.699
Duration of disease (Months)	-0.222	0.118	0.407	0.003
Duration of Rx (week)	-0.074	0.607	0.01	0.942
UCT Total	-0.474	<0.001	1	
All cases n = 101	USS Total	P-value	UCT Total	P-value
Group B n = 50				
Age	0.174	0.227	-0.015	0.918
BMI	0.053	0.715	-0.046	0.749
No. of SE	0.277	0.051	-0.166	0.249
Duration of disease (months)	0.238	0.096	-0.283	0.047
Duration of Rx (week)	0.066	0.652	-0.136	0.351
UCT Total	-0.653	<0.001	1	

P value by Spearman's rho.

exposure to heat or specific food additives is not confined by geographical boundaries and may affect individuals within diverse populations (Lee and Bernstein 2025).

Treatment protocols and anticipated side effect

The present study exhibited markedly different therapy characteristics between the two study groups, suggesting distinct treatment patterns reflecting a stepwise escalation strategy for CSU. In the current study, most patients used Second-generation H1-antihistamines, however, prescribed more often with patients on combination therapy, conforming to international guidelines that recommend second-generation antihistamines as first-line therapy given their better safety profile and benefit–risk ratio (de Silva et al. 2014). The relative predominance of second-generation antihistamines in combination therapy group may represent efforts to maximize symptom control in patients who did not find relief with monotherapy. A recent review reported that approximately 61% of CSU patients exhibit a lack of response to standard permitted doses of second-generation H1-antihistamines, among those, non-responders, approximately 63% derive benefits at a higher dosage (Rayner et al. 2024). For patients who do not react to normal non-sedating antihistamine treatment, the American Urticaria Guidelines advocate combining or increasing the dose, to effectively treat CSU, practitioners often prescribe non-sedating antihistamine in the morning and a sedating first-generation H1-antihistamine, such as hydroxyzine, at night to minimize night-time itch and improve sleep, as sedation helps patients sleep better despite the itching (Sussman et al. 2018). Research on H2 antihistamines has yielded inconsistent findings. Cimetidine as H2 antihistamines inhibits certain cytochrome P-450 enzymes, which impacts hydroxyzine metabolism and results in elevated levels of this first-generation H1-antihistamines in the bloodstream (Lee and Bernstein 2025). It is believed that this impaired hydroxyzine metabolism underlies its

synergistic effect, resulting in clinical improvement (Lee and Bernstein 2025). However, data demonstrates moderate benefit with leukotriene receptor antagonists in specially selected patients and those with Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drug (NSAID)-exacerbated urticaria (Weller et al. 2025). The US guidelines' second step includes leukotriene receptor antagonist (LTRAs), which include drugs like montelukast (Lee and Bernstein 2025). Research has yielded inconsistent findings in previous studies indicated that leukotriene receptor antagonist (LTRAs) may lead to symptom improvement compared to placebo, while others found no significant difference (Lee and Bernstein 2025). A recent meta-analysis examined 34 randomized controlled trials that assessing the impact of LTRAs in CU and concluded that the addition of LTRAs yielded modest benefits (Wagner et al. 2021). Corticosteroids were administered to patients with combination therapy only and were used as a short-term rescue therapy in severe or uncontrolled disease and not as a maintenance treatment. International guidelines recommend a short-term use of corticosteroids sparingly during acute exacerbations with clear documentation of their damaging effects with long-term use (Maurer et al. 2020).

Medications used in the current study revealed drowsiness was the predominant side effect, especially in the combination therapy group, which also exhibited elevated incidences of fatigue, dizziness, relative to monotherapy. These results are consistent with a randomized clinical trial in India, which showed that that sedation-related adverse events were the most common side effect among those using levocetirizine and hydroxyzine due to their binding to H1 receptors in the brain (Ali et al. 2024).

Assessment of disease severity and associated factors

Although the Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) is recommended by the international guidelines for assessing disease activity in CSU (Zuberbier et al. 2022), its use in this

study was limited by poor patient adherence. In this study, the USS was used to assess how severe the disease was. The findings for both study groups were generally comparable and did not show significant differences, suggesting similar overall disease severity and perceived impact, despite differences in the intensity of pharmacological treatment at the time of the survey. This underscores a clinical aspect of CSU, greater intensity of pharmacotherapy do not necessarily lead to lower perceived burden of disease.

In the current study, Angioedema was the strongest predictor of severity. Consistent with this finding data from the large, international ASSURE-CSU study showed that patients with angioedema had more severe CSU and a significantly worse health-related quality of life, and greater impairment in emotional well-being compared to those without angioedema (Sussman et al. 2018). Number of reported exacerbating factors appeared to influence USS severity, as patients reporting a single trigger exhibited lower USS than those reporting none. Current international urticaria guidance recognizes that, in CSU, many patients have no identifiable trigger, whereas others identify non-specific factors that may worsen symptoms intermittently rather than act as true causes (Zuberbier et al. 2022). Accordingly, documenting and selectively avoiding relevant triggers can reduce flares, but strict avoidance may impair quality of life. Patient-reported triggers are prone to misclassification, as coincidental exposures may be blamed while clinically important factors, such as NSAIDs or stress, can be overlooked without structured assessment.

Assessment of disease control and associated factors

The majority of patients in both study group exhibited uncontrolled disease status as assessed with the UCT with only 16/101 patients being well controlled, and no significant difference between study group. These findings reflect the burden of disease despite ongoing management. This is consistent with recent studies indicating that most patients with CSU reported inadequate disease control (Weller et al. 2025). Such uncontrolled rate aligns with large real-world data, indicating that a significant proportion of CSU patients remain uncontrolled in routine care, often despite ongoing treatment (Maurer et al. 2020; Wagner et al. 2021). It further reflects observational findings that the translation between guidelines and practice is a gap that perpetuates a symptom burden and impaired outcomes (Wagner et al. 2021). Providing patients with adequate education about their condition and effective coping strategies is essential for improving symptom control and treatment outcomes (Ali et al. 2024).

In the current study a notable association emerged between age and disease control status, with the highest proportion of uncontrolled cases occurring in young adults and a greater share of well-controlled disease among patients aged 40–64 years. This pattern is clinically plausible because CSU control reflects a dynamic interaction

between disease biology, adherence, and health-seeking behaviors rather than demographics alone, and younger adults often report higher psychosocial burden that can impair perceived control and treatment persistence.

Finally, the current study indicates that UCT was negatively correlated with USS, indicating that higher disease activity is linked to poorer control. It is also remarking the opposite association of disease duration and control, the longer the disease duration, the higher UCT with patients on monotherapy ($r = 0.407$), but the opposite with patients on combination therapy ($r = -0.283$). This bidirectional phenomenon is clinically plausible since duration could equally represent positive longitudinal adaptation and self-management (improving perceived control) or a persistent refractory course where longstanding disease may cause transiently uncontrolled symptoms despite therapy.

Study limitations

When interpreting the findings of the present study, it must be borne in mind that several limitations were present. First, the cross-sectional design of the study limits causal inferences about relationships between treatment modalities and disease severity or control, since data were collected at a single time point without longitudinal follow-up. Second, the sample size was relatively small and the two health-care centers recruited from were located within Baghdad, limiting the generalizability of the findings to the population of the wider Iraq or other potential settings in the region with differing demographic and clinical aspects. Third, disease severity and control were assessed using patient-reported questionnaires such as the Urticaria Severity Score (USS) and the Urticaria Control Test (UCT) which may entail recall bias and subjective interpretation by the participants. Finally, the use of advanced biologic therapies such as omalizumab was restricted in the study environment because of financial constraints, which may have influenced the treatment strategies and degree of disease control among patients.

Conclusion

A significant proportion of patients in this cross-sectional study had poor disease control. An inverse correlation was found between disease severity and disease control; that is, the higher the severity, the lower the disease control. These results show that the burden of CSU persists clinically, and underscore the importance of adopting detailed and personalized treatment plans for each patient according to their condition.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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